

Beauty Salon Appointment System

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Abstract. The Beauty Salon Appointment System is a web-based application designed to manage the daily operations of a beauty salon more efficiently. This System is a centralized platform that integrates essential functions such as appointment booking, staff scheduling, service management, and inventory control. Additionally, it allows for efficient management of users and customers, manage various payment types and processes, maintains payment records, and handles promotions. The system features different user roles_admin, staff, and customers each with specific access and functions.

Keywords: appointment, customer, payment type, staff

INTRODUCTION

In today's rapidly evolving beauty industry, meeting the changing needs of customers requires efficient and effective management. Utilizing technology to provide faster, more convenient services have become essential for salon businesses to stay competitive. The Beauty Salon Management System is an online tool designed to help administrators efficiently manage salon services and client appointments. With a user-friendly interface, the system ensures that salon staff and admin can provide high-quality services effectively and efficiently. By replacing traditional manual methods with a digital solution, the system minimizes errors, improves workflow, and ensures that customers receive a smooth and professional experience from booking to service completion.

PROBLEM

In beauty salons, improper appointment scheduling and time management can lead to double bookings, no-shows, and long waiting lines. Incomplete customer records, failure to note customer preferences, and the inability to maintain loyalty customers are also common issues. Additionally, inaccurate staff schedules, improper task allocation, and insufficient training can result in inconsistent service quality, which may harm the salon's reputation and customer satisfaction. In terms of accounting and finance, inaccurate sales records, lack of timely knowledge about sales and expenses, and poor management of promotions and discounts can reduce business profitability. Manual record-keeping can also lead to time wastage, data loss, and the inability to generate reports, making business management even more difficult.

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APPROACH

This system consists of two roles: User and Administrator. User can easily look at the home page the information and also view about page, service page. Moreover, user needs to have account if the user wants to take the appointment booking. If the user has an account, go to login page. In this page, the user must fill email and password. If email and password are the same in data from database, the user can choose service type and make appointment. And the user can view appointment list. The user can log out from the system if the user wants to log out.

Firstly, the admin log in to the system and then, check email and password. When they are correct, the admin view dashboard. In dashboard page, the admin can see all of the counts for services, staff and appointments. And the admin can manage staff and also does customer. Furthermore, the admin can manage service. When the user takes the booking appointments, the admin can manage this appointments. The admin can manage payment type and also view payment. The admin can manage promotion and also generate pdf file. In this file, the system shows the appointments information. And the admin can log out from the system that the admin wants to log out.

Figure 1: System Flow Diagram

Figure 2: Database Design

An Entity Relationship Diagram uses data modeling techniques that can help define business processes and serve as the foundation for a relational database. An Entity Relationship Diagram attribute can be denoted as a primary key, which identifies a unique attribute, or a foreign key, which can be assigned to multiple attributes. In database, an ER diagram for an airline reservation system shows how the databases are connected. It also shows how all the databases are logically related to each other. We can also create an ER diagram by drawing the figure of a different part of the airline reservation system, their properties, and how they perform their task. The figure 2 shows database design for all the data tables and their relationship of the database.

RESULTS

The implementation of the Beauty Salon Appointment System has significantly improved the efficiency and organization of salon operations. Appointment scheduling is now more accurate, reducing double bookings and minimizing customer waiting times. Customer records are well-maintained, allowing personalized services and better loyalty management. Additionally, the system’s user-friendly interface makes it easy for both staff and customers to navigate, enhancing the overall service experience and increasing customer satisfaction. Overall, the system has streamlined operations, improved accuracy, and contributed to the salon’s growth and profitability.

Figure 3: Implementation of this system

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the Beauty Salon Appointment System has proven to be an effective solution for modernizing salon operations and enhancing overall service quality. By automating key processes such as appointment scheduling, customer management, the system reduces manual errors, saves time, and improves operational efficiency. Its user-friendly interface ensures ease of use for both staff and customers, while the centralized database provides reliable information for informed decision-making. This system helps customers, staff, and admin easily schedule appointments and efficiently manage services. It improves business efficiency and customer satisfaction while providing essential data to support business growth. Overall, the system not only streamlines daily operations but also supports business growth, customer satisfaction, and long-term profitability, making it a valuable tool for any beauty salon.

REFERENCES

- [1] Kotler, P., & Keller, K. L. (2016). Marketing Management (15th ed.). Pearson Education.
- [2] Laudon, K. C., & Laudon, J. P. (2018). Management Information Systems: Managing the Digital Firm (15th ed.). Pearson.
- [3] Stair, R., & Reynolds, G. (2020). Principles of Information Systems (13th ed.). Cengage Learning.
- [4] Kumar, Anuj. Beauty Salon Management System using PHP and MySQL. PHPGurukul, 2019.
- [5] Mosmj. Beauty Salon Management System in PHP and MySQLi. Mozello, 2020.